

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

First Canadian Living Labs Summit

**November 6-7, 2023
Montreal**

**Thomson House,
McGill University
3650 Mc Tavish St, Montreal, Quebec**

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

CANADIAN LIVING LABS SUMMIT 2023

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) was established in 2006 by the European Commission under the Finnish Presidency. It aims to foster global development of Living Labs as open innovation ecosystems that emphasize co-creation and cross-border & cross-sectoral collaboration. ENoLL's mission is to offer value to its members and stakeholders by enhancing capacities and knowledge. While primarily a European network with 80% of its members based in Europe, it has a global reach, including significant engagement in Canada.

Canada's involvement with ENoLL dates back to the early days, notably with the RehabMaLL, the first Living Lab in Rehabilitation, founded in Quebec in 2011. This initiative was supported by the Fonds Recherche Quebec Santé (FRQS) and the Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation (CRIR). Since then, the presence and impact of Living Labs have expanded dramatically in Canada. The country now boasts over 100 Living Labs across diverse sectors including environment, agriculture, forestry, marine life, urban development, sustainability, and health. These Labs are situated in various settings such as universities, research centers, and community-based organizations.

The inaugural Canadian Living Lab Summit, held in Montreal in November 2023, was hosted by McGill University and co-organized by ENoLL, McGill, and the University of Montreal. The summit provided a unique platform for participants to exchange ideas, forge collaborations, and strengthen the Living Lab ecosystem. This event highlighted the vibrant Living Lab activities across Canada and emphasized opportunities for cross-border and cross-sectoral partnerships, particularly between Canadian and European Living Labs. The summit's objectives included promoting the Living Lab methodology, showcasing Canadian initiatives, supporting networking and knowledge exchange, and drafting Policy Recommendations for Canadian Policy Makers.

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

AGENDA

Day 1: Monday November 6, 2023

8:30	Registration and Coffee
9:00	Welcome and Introductions Eva Kehayia & Cyril Duclos (co-organisers) Sylvain Baillet, Associate Dean, Research McGill University / Ekat Kritikou, Vice-Dean, Research and Development, Université de Montréal / Martina Desole, Director ENoLL
9:15	Why Living Labs <i>When and why should we use Living Lab methodology? What is ENoLL?</i> Evdokimos Konstantinidis, President ENoLL
9:30	Round Table 1. Setting the Scene: The CANADIAN Approach <i>Understanding the Canadian approach towards Living Labs. (Policy Session)</i> Ted Hewitt - President, SSHRC François Chrétien - Director chrRTD, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada AAFC Carole Jabet - Scientific Director, Fonds de recherche du Québec FRQS Janice Bailey - Scientific Director, Fonds de recherche du Québec FRQNT Marie-Pierre Cosette - Director, Fonds de recherche du Québec FRQSC Hasna Rouighi - Director of Innovation, Ministry of Health and Social Services Quebec Maria Pawlowska - International R&D Partnerships, VISNEA <i>Moderated by: Martina Desole, Director ENoLL</i>
11:00	<i>Coffee Break</i>
11:15	Showcasing Living Labs Marie-Pierre Faure - Director Innovation Support, TransMedTech Institute of Montreal Sara Ahmed - Lead Researcher, BRILLIANT François Chrétien - Director RTD AAFC, AGRIFOOD LL, The Canadian Agroecosystem Living Labs Network (CALLNET) Panagiotis Bamidis - Lead Researcher, ThessAHALL Tania Zamuner & Christopher T. Fennell - Lead Researchers, UOttawa LL <i>Moderated by Eva Kehayia</i>
12:30	Canadian Network of Labs (CANEOLABS) March, 2024
12:35	Networking Lunch

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

13:45	<p>Showcasing Living Labs</p> <p>Raquel Peñalosa - President of Mandalab of Communautique Mike Thususka - Director of Economic Development, Summerside PEI François Routhier - Social Participation and Inclusive Cities Karina Lebel - Researcher, Human-Robot Symbiosis (HuRoS) Bénédicte D'Anjou - Research Coordinator, É-LABO Mélanie Couture - Lead Researcher, Smart Environments Supporting the Ecosystem of Fragile and Isolated Seniors: The City of Côte Saint-Luc Living Lab</p> <p><i>Moderated by Cyril Duclos</i></p>
15:15	<p>Round Table 2. Living Labs within Universities, Research Centres and Networks <i>Clarifying the role of research in Living Labs</i></p> <p>Debra Titone - Associate Vice-Principal, Research McGill University Ekat Kritikou - Vice-Dean, Research and Development, Université de Montréal (tbc) Philippe Archambault et Claudine Auger - Co-scientific directors, Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of Greater Montreal (CRIR) François Routhier - Scientific director, Réseau provincial de recherche en adaptation-réadaptaton (REPAR) Gary Libben - Professor of Applied Linguistics, Brock University Sabrina Boutin - Principal VP, MEDTEQ+ Consortium Karina Lebel - Researcher, Human-Robot Symbiosis (HuRoS), INTER Jean-François Jasmin - Project manager, Laboratoire en innovation ouverte LLIO</p> <p><i>Moderated by: Bonnie Swaine, Director of the School of rehabilitation, Université de Montréal</i></p>
16:30	<p>Conclusions and Closure of Day 1 – Eva Kehayia & Cyril Duclos</p>

Day 2: Tuesday November 7, 2023

8:30	<p>Arrival and Coffee</p>
8:45	<p>Harmonization of Living Labs (VITALISE)</p> <p>Despoina Petsani, Nancy Azevedo, Panagiotis Bamidis, Martina Desole, Eva Kehayia, Evdokimos Konstatinidis, Francesca Spagnoli</p>

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

9:15	<p>Showcasing Living Labs</p> <p>Martha King - Creative Director Knowle West Media Centre, Bristol Living Lab Annie Côté, Séverine Parent, Ève Pouliot - Lead researchers, LaVIE Ann Galbraith - Smart Cities Project Manager, City of Calgary Eva Kehayia - RehabMALL and VITALISE in Montreal Chantal Rossignol - Coordinator, Écosystème de laboratoires d'accélération en économie circulaire (CERIEC)</p> <p><i>Moderated by Nancy Azevedo</i></p>
10:30	<i>Coffee Break</i>
11:00	<p>Round Table 3. Living Labs Everyday Reality</p> <p><i>Challenges and facilitators, needs, desires and means to succeed when conducting Living Lab research</i></p> <p>Chantal Rossignol - Coordinator, Écosystème de laboratoires d'accélération en économie circulaire (CERIEC) Tania Zamuner - Lead Researcher, UOttawa LL Ann Galbraith - Smart Cities Project Manager, City of Calgary (tbc) Martha King - Creative Director, Knowle West Media Centre, Bristol Living Lab Marie-Pierre Faure - Director Innovation Support, TransMedTech Institute of Montreal (tbc) Eric Racine - Director, Unité de recherche en éthique pragmatique de la santé, Institut de recherches cliniques de Montréal (IRCM) É-LABO</p> <p>Moderated by: Rachel Berthiaume, Co-coordinator, Laboratoire en innovation ouverte LLIO</p>
12:45	Closing Remarks – Eva Kehayia & Cyril Duclos
13:00	End of the Summit

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

PANEL SUMMARIES

PANEL 1 – SETTING THE SCENE: THE CANADIAN APPROACH

Understanding the Canadian approach towards Living Labs (LL). (Policy Session)

Moderator: Martina Desole (ENoLL)

Participants:

Ted Hewitt – President SSHRC

Carole Jabet – Scientific Director FRQS

Janice Bailey - Scientific Director FRQNT

Marie-Pierre Cosette (MPC) – Director FRQSC

François Chrétien - Director Research, Development and Technology AAFC

Maria Pawlowska (VISNEA)

The Panel began with an introduction by the moderator, Martina Desole who spoke about the concept and overall philosophy of Living Labs (LL) as dynamic platforms for experimentation, creation, and development of innovative solutions within real-life environments through co-creation and synergistic action between all interested parties.

Following a short introduction when each panelist presented themselves or their organization/agency, three main questions were addressed:

- 1) What do you perceive as the role and relevance of Living Labs within the Canadian landscape?
- 2) Do your current initiatives include funding for Living Labs, and if not, are you exploring the possibility of introducing such programs in the future?
- 3) Considering the evidence-based policy approach and your program cycle, what particular insights or feedback from living labs, universities, and researchers do you consider essential when making decisions about investments in living labs?

Responding to the first question, '*What do you perceive as the role and relevance of living labs within the Canadian landscape?*', overall, all panelists acknowledged the importance of breaking silos, supporting community-based research, working with communities and end users, connecting with the research community, tackling global societal challenges, promoting intersectoriality, and accelerating innovation. These statements are also reflected in the strategic planning and new funding programs both at the federal (SSHRC) and provincial (FRQS, FRQSC, FRQNT) levels. While the concept of Living Labs is relatively new to the funding agencies, current related programs respond to the need of the researchers and

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

communities for funding of Living Lab type research. Similarly, Agrifood Canada operates on the premise of fostering connections with the end-users to facilitate the adoption of innovation and increase the impact of research. Finally, VISNEA stressed the importance of embracing Open Science through policies and legislation.

Turning to the second question, *'Do your current initiatives include funding for Living Labs, and if not, are you exploring the possibility of introducing such programs in the future'*, even though not all agencies fund Living Lab research, they all support community/partnership-based research designed to find solutions on the ground. Fund directors acknowledged that proper (appropriate instead of proper) funding is essential for the creation of partnerships and stressed the importance of demonstrating that the ensuing research and deliverables benefit the partner and implementing solutions on the ground. The panelists stressed the importance of true partnerships with the genuine participation of all interested parties. Finally, panelists raised the need for policies supporting research in partnership with diverse communities.

Finally, in answering question 3, *'Considering the evidence-based policy approach and your program cycle, what particular insights or feedback from living labs, universities, and researchers do you consider essential when making decisions about investments in living labs?'*, all panelists agreed that things need to be done differently: from the way projects are funded to the way knowledge is mobilized and the way research impact is measured. The importance of identifying the relevant parameters to measure impact as well as creating a new framework for evaluation that could alleviate concerns of researchers desiring to do Living Lab research but fearing a negative evaluation was reiterated by all panelists. Finally, six main points were brought forward by the FRQS: 1) What is the space, how can one envision training of students? 2) What is the timing? How long should one fund a LL to truly foster working together? 3) With regard to research assessment, while acknowledging that something needs to change, what that is remains unclear. How does one rephrase the evaluation criteria? The words that are used are very important. 4) How to ensure certification (LL recognition)? 5) How do LLs report and ensure fair principles and scale up? 6) How to engage stakeholders? What are the key factors of success?

At the end of the session, the panelists answered questions from the floor with two main themes prevailing: 1) sustainability of Living Labs and 2) breaking down existing silos between funding agencies. In response to the first question, the importance of planning ways to ensure sustainability through funding was brought forward. In response to the second question, the directors of the different agencies stated that while they are already working together to ensure fluid communication and concerted planning, more can be done in the future.

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

PANEL 2 – LIVING LABS WITHIN UNIVERSITIES, RESEARCH CENTRES AND NETWORKS

Clarifying the role of research in Living Labs

Moderated by: Bonnie Swaine, Director of the School of Rehabilitation, Université de Montréal

Participants

Debra Titone - Associate Vice-Principal, Research McGill University

Ekat Kritikou - Vice-Dean, Research and Development, Université de Montréal (tbc)

Gary Libben - Professor of Applied Linguistics, Brock University

Philippe Archambault and Claudine Auger - Co-scientific directors, Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of Greater Montreal (CRIR)

François Routhier - Scientific director, Réseau provincial de recherche en adaptation-réadaptation (REPAR)

Sabrina Boutin - Principal VP, MEDTEQ+ Consortium

Karina Lebel - Researcher, Human-Robot Symbiosis (HuRoS)

Jean-François Jasmin - Project manager, Laboratoire en innovation ouverte LLIO

Following each panelist's short introduction of themselves and of their organization, three main questions were addressed:

- 1) What do you perceive as the role of your organization (be it a university, research center or network) with respect to Living Labs in the Quebec/Canadian context?
- 2) Do your current initiatives include support (financial or otherwise) for Living Labs, and if so, can you tell us more about your support, and if not, are you exploring the possibility of introducing such programs in the future?
- 3) Do you think Living Labs can help you or your organization better define programs and initiatives? In other words, what particular information (or performance outcomes, anticipated or real) from Living Labs, universities, and researchers do you consider essential when making decisions about supporting or investments in Living Labs?

Universities, research centres and research networks do not directly fund the creation of Living Labs. Rather they support Living Lab initiatives by providing resources (cash or in kind) for research data management, research platforms, information sharing, and knowledge transfer initiatives. They promote collaborations with different interested parties and help in creating partnerships. They also provide seed funding for intersectoral projects and create collaborative spaces for students.

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

An important concern raised by the panelists pertained to the sustainability of intersectoral projects and Living Labs. Panelists acknowledged the importance of developing strategies to ensure that Living Labs continue to live beyond the initial period of funding. Such strategies may include providing mentorship for applications to diverse funding agencies and building bridges between public and private funding sources.

Finally, when addressing the types of key performance outcomes/indicators that would help guide funding decisions for Living Lab initiatives among universities, research centres and networks, all panelists stressed the importance including both qualitative and quantitative performance indicators. Among the qualitative indicators are the coherence, vibrancy and collaboration among the team members, the active involvement of community partners, and the presence (existence?) of value added for all interested parties. Finally, they also stressed the importance of providing learning opportunities for researchers, students and partners, and of being flexible, agile, adaptive and resilient.

PANEL 3 – LIVING LABS EVERYDAY REALITY

Challenges and facilitators, needs, desires and means to succeed when conducting Living Lab Research

Moderated by: Rachel Berthiaume, Co-coordinator, Laboratoire en innovation ouverte LLIO

Participants

Chantal Rossignol - Coordinator, Écosystème de laboratoires d'accélération en économie circulaire (CERIEC)

Ann Galbraith - Smart Cities Project Manager, City of Calgary

Martha King - Creative Director, Knowle West Media Centre, Bristol Living Lab

Marie-Pierre Faure - Director Innovation & Living Lab TransMedTech Institute of Montreal

Eric Racine - Director, Unité de recherche en éthique pragmatique de la santé, Institut de recherches cliniques de Montréal (IRCM) É-LABO

1. Is your Living Lab user driven or human centered? What are difficulties in engaging users in the Living Labs? What is needed to increase user involvement in the process?
2. How do you integrate stakeholder diversities in the Living Lab.
3. In the Living Lab approach, we want to integrate the quadruple helix partnerships (Public, Private, research, Person). And how do you engage the different partners in the process?

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

4. How do you inform the partners that it is possible to have no output (tangible output, like a product or a service)? In this type of process, can there be a problem in delivering an output? And if yes, why is there such a problem?
5. What is your wish for Living Labs in Canada?

All panelists stated that they primarily use a user-driven approach with a “human centered” broader perspective. The term “planet centered” was also mentioned to ensure including the entire environment.

When referring to difficulties engaging partners in the living labs, panelists highlighted the importance of sensitizing the public to the Living Lab approach and the methods used, as the lack of familiarity breeds resistance and at times fear of engaging.

All panelists stressed the importance of ensuring that partner needs and desires be taken into account, ensuring added value for all. Using vocabulary that is easily understood by all was stressed as key to developing a clear and common understanding. Being able to speak multiple “languages” (i.e. Adapting their vocabulary to each stakeholder) was raised as an asset. Similarly, using platform(s) that suit the partners’ abilities and needs was also seen as crucial.

Turning to the integration of partner diversities in the Living Lab, panelists pointed out the importance of creating a common ground for conversation, holding in-person events, one-on-one conversations as well as group meetings, removing hierarchical barriers and creating a feeling of trust and equality among the partners. Finally, in order to ensure continued and sustained engagement, keeping regular communication with partners, providing status reports, managing outcome expectations, and adjusting processes and expectations when needed were all seen as important to ensuring a healthy relationship within the Living Lab.

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Needs of Living Labs in Canada: Supporting a Living Lab Culture while/by Diversifying Funding Opportunities

Living Labs (LLs) in Canada play a crucial role in fostering innovation and collaboration to address real-world challenges. However, to thrive and maximize their impact, LLs require greater support from Funding Agencies. This document outlines key areas where Funding Agencies can provide such support, creating a more robust and impactful ecosystem for LLs as an outcome of the “First Canadian Living Labs Summit” organized by McGill University, University of Montreal, and ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs.

Beyond traditional project-based grants, LLs require a more diverse funding landscape. Dedicated funding programs specifically designed for LL initiatives would be highly beneficial. Additionally, support for partnership-based research projects that align with the core principles of the LL approach, even when not explicitly named as such, is crucial. These core principles include collaboration, co-creation, and a focus on real-life environment problem-solving. Funding Agencies can also recognize and fund programs that embody these principles, fostering a broader understanding of the LL approach.

1. **Promote Funding Flexibility:** Prioritize allocating resources to support community-based research and Living Labs (LLs) initiatives, acknowledging their role in driving innovation and addressing real-world challenges. Encourage funding that allows for flexibility in project design and implementation, requesting collaboration between researchers, industries, public administrations, communities, and end-users. Emphasize the importance of funding models that support co-creation and co-design processes, enabling stakeholders to actively participate in shaping research agendas and outcomes.
2. **Enhance Intersectoral Collaboration (quadruple/quintuple helix):** Allocate resources to support initiatives that foster collaboration between different sectors, including academia, industry, government, and communities. Recognize the value of interdisciplinary approaches in addressing complex societal challenges and breaking down silos between disciplines. Encourage partnerships that leverage diverse expertise and perspectives, maximizing the impact of research outcomes and promoting innovation.
3. **Prioritize Interdisciplinary Research:** Incentivize projects that promote interdisciplinary research approaches, bringing together experts from various fields to address multifaceted issues. Allocate resources to support collaborative efforts that

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

bridge traditional disciplinary boundaries and encourage open innovative solutions. Emphasize the importance of funding programs that promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange, driving impactful research outcomes.

4. **Invest in Capacity Building:** Allocate resources for capacity building initiatives to promote the LL approach and to empower researcher, community, and stakeholder involvement. Support training programs, workshops, and collaborative networks that enhance skills, knowledge, and expertise in co-creation and co-design methodologies. Recognize the importance of investing in human capital to build sustainable research ecosystems and foster a culture of innovation and collaboration.
5. **Support Sustainable Living Labs Infrastructure:** Recognize the critical role of infrastructure in supporting the long-term sustainability of LL initiatives. Allocate resources for the development of physical spaces, staffing, and other necessary resources to support ongoing LL activities. Emphasize the importance of investing in infrastructure that enables collaboration, knowledge sharing, and innovation, ensuring the continued effectiveness of LL initiatives over time.
6. **Revise Evaluation Criteria:** Reevaluate the criteria used to assess research impact, moving beyond traditional metrics like impact factors and publications. Consider alternative methods for evaluating the success of LL initiatives, such as community engagement, knowledge mobilization, and societal impact. Emphasize the importance of measuring outcomes that reflect the real-world impact of research, including its relevance to communities and stakeholders.
7. **Facilitate Knowledge Mobilization:** Support initiatives that utilize creative strategies for disseminating research results and knowledge generated from LLs to diverse audiences. Allocate resources for communication channels such as plays, musicals, books, and digital platforms that reach broader communities effectively. Emphasize the importance of engaging with stakeholders to ensure that research findings are accessible, relevant, and actionable.
8. **Promote Open Science Principles:** Support the adoption of Open Science principles within LL initiatives, promoting transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration in research practices. Allocate resources for the development of policies and infrastructure that facilitate the involvement of diverse communities, including Indigenous perspectives, in research processes. Encourage practices that promote data sharing, reproducibility, and ethical conduct, fostering a culture of openness and accountability.

First Canadian Living Lab Summit

Montreal, 6 – 7 November 2023

9. **Ensure Stakeholder Engagement:** Emphasize the importance of stakeholder engagement in LL initiatives, recognizing communities, industry partners, and various stakeholders as valuable contributors to the research process. Create opportunities for meaningful dialogue and collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring that research priorities are aligned with the needs and interests of end-users. Encourage inclusive decision-making processes that promote equity, diversity, and mutual learning.
10. **Encourage International Collaboration:** Foster partnerships and collaboration on LL initiatives at the international level, recognizing the global nature of many societal challenges. Facilitate knowledge exchange, funding opportunities, and best practice sharing between countries, leveraging diverse perspectives and expertise in LL research. Encourage cross-border collaborations that address shared challenges and promote innovation on a global scale.